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Dear

In May 2021, after writing a project proposal for a 2-years postdoc through the Lise Meitner Program (FWF), you proposed to extend the project to support a PhD student of yours and receive more funding for additional operations, suggesting I would be leading the development of the project. During our first meeting on 10 March 2021, you reiterated to leave the leading of the project to us, and in the following two months you repeatedly expressed great satisfaction for the quick progresses. However, a sudden change would soon happen in our operating system, finding myself isolated and unheard.

The change happened during a process of analysis at the beginning of April, and specifically after presenting a proposal in two consequent web-meetings where I suggested that sonic transitions between pitched and noisy sounds may provoke a perception of closure – a thesis in perfect line with the FWF original project. During the first meeting, you asked me for more examples to support the thesis. During the second meeting, I provided you with a list of examples to visualize the possible phenomenon and support it through musical literature, which was rejected by you

. I had to research on such topics by myself, coming to complete an experiment on noise and closures that I am currently transforming into an article without physical or moral support from my own team, contributing to support operations in the project for which you act as principal investigator. Such original directions on processes and noises are also reported in a paper prepared for an internal meeting on 10.3.2021, currently available in our Dropbox folder.

I don't really know what happened, but I was suddenly excluded from the design of both the research and the platform,

I cannot keep living for a career, but I understood that it's time to also live for happiness. This is not appealing when all my contributions and observations keep being ignored. I ask therefore to let me work remotely from Italy, and come to Graz every six to eight weeks. This would allow me to set a stable life. During this time, I would contribute to your project, following your directions but acting as an advisor, so providing feedback only when I am asked to, because I feel that it would hurt me less and would provide a better environment for everybody to work. I would conduct my personal research two days per weeks, as I would like to bring a little forward my personal research on cadences, noise, and entropy, which will contribute to the overall FWF project. If this was not possible, I will confirm my resignation in around November.

Yours faithfully

Luca